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Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Transdermal Patches of Meloxicam by Solvent Casting Method

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to formulate and evaluate meloxicam transdermal patches using Hydroxypropyl Cellulose (HPC) as the sole polymer, aiming to provide a controlled release system for effective pain management. Because meloxicam, a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), causes gastrointestinal side effects and has low oral bioavailability, transdermal delivery is an ideal alternative. To improve flexibility propylene glycol was used as a plasticizer in the formulation. Drug content, moisture content, moisture uptake, folding endurance, flatness, thickness, weight variation, and in vitro drug release studies were tested. Due to the hydrophilic nature of HPC, findings indicated that patches based on HPC contained more moisture content and moisture uptake, which increased drug release and flexibility of the film. Controlled and sustained release of meloxicam was proven through the in vitro release tests, suggesting the potential for longer-lasting therapeutic effects with fewer side effects. The research revealed that transdermal patches with HPC have showed sufficient stability and bioavailability.

INTRODUCTION

Compared to the preceding two decades, changes in the area of medical delivery are taking place much faster now. Better patient compliance and an important aspect of new methods of drug delivery is effectiveness(1,2). Exploring more recent body interfaces for drug delivery has been an extreme approach. One of these is transdermal drug delivery, which utilizes human skin as a portal for

the systemic administration of medication molecules. Among the devices that fall into the category of controlled drug delivery is the transdermal drug delivery system, or TDDS, whose purpose is to administer the medication through the skin at a precise and regulated pace.(1) TDDS is a painless technique that applies a drug formulation to healthy, unbroken skin to distribute medication systemically(3,4). Without

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accumulating in the dermal layer, the medication first penetrates the stratum corneum before moving on to the deeper epidermis and dermis. Drugs can be absorbed systemically through the dermal microcirculation once they reach the dermal layer(5,6). Compared to other traditional drug delivery methods, TDDS has numerous benefits(7–10). Meloxicam (mlx) belongs to the family of oxicam chemicals. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA), osteoarthritis (OA), and juvenile RA are all treated with it because to its analgesic, antipyretic, and anti-inflammatory qualities. On the market, it is available in parenteral and oral dosage forms. Although mlx is generally well tolerated, it does cause some side effects, the most prevalent of which are gastrointestinal. The oral dosage ranges from 7.5 to 15 mg. The goal of this research is to develop a dissolvable patches for meloxicam (MLX) that has higher penetration bypassing the systemic circulation and analyze the various materials needed to optimize the formula. The mixture was poured in a petri dish. The patch was chopped into smaller patches that resulted from a mold after it had dried completely. The objective of this study is to create meloxicam (MLX) dissolvable patches with greater penetration that avoid the systemic circulation and to examine the different components required to optimize the formula. A petri dish was used to cast the mixture. After the patch had completely dried, it was cut into smaller patches that were the result of a mold (11).

Epidemiology of rheumatoid arthritis Osteoarthritis

According to the Arthritis Foundation, 32.5 million people in the US and 500 million people globally (about 7% of the world's population) suffer with osteoarthritis (OA). According to the Arthritis Foundation, osteoarthritis affects 15% of adults over 60 worldwide. The sixth most prevalent disability worldwide is osteoarthritis. A review published in *The Lancet Discovery Science* in November 2020 found that four-fifths of the global OA burden is caused by knee osteoarthritis. According to the Osteoarthritis Action Alliance, physicians in the United States conduct one million knee and hip replacement procedures annually due to OA.

Rheumatoid arthritis

According to the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation's 2019 Global Burden of Disease research, Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) affects over 18 million people globally. According to the American College of Rheumatology, about 1.3 million Americans suffer from RA. Of those with RA, around 75% are allocated female at birth (AFAB). According to the Arthritis Foundation, 6.4 million ambulatory (non-hospital) visits globally resulted in a diagnosis of RA in 2011. In 1990, 2.1 million adults in the US suffered from RA. According to the National Arthritis Workgroup, this figure has probably decreased as a result of fewer cases and more stringent classification standards.

Fig 1. Epidemiology of Arthritis

Material and preparation:

The API and excipients (table 1) were collected from the laboratory of Dr. D. Y. Patil college of pharmacy, Akurdi.

Table 1: List Of Materials Used

Sr. no.	Material used
1.	Meloxicam
2.	Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)
3.	Hydroxyl propyl cellulose (HPC)
4.	Ethanol
5.	Propylene glycol
6.	Glycerin

Preparation of transdermal films:

Meloxicam transdermal patches were prepared by solvent casting technique in petri plate.

The backing membrane was prepared by pouring a 2 % (w/v) polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) solution followed by drying at 60 °c for 6 h.

The drug reservoir was prepared by dissolving HPC in ethanol (8ml)

Add 5-6 drops of propylene glycol used as plasticizer

Drug is dissolve in another container was added to the reservoir under slow stirring with magnetic stirrer

The mixture was spread over PVA film and dried at room temperature

Table 2: Composition Of Transdermal Patches

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Formulation code		
		F1	F2	F3
1.	Drug (mg)	50	50	50
2.	HPC	200 mg	250 mg	250 mg
3.	polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)	2gm	2gm	2gm
4.	Propylene glycol	5-6 drop	5-6 drop	5-6 drop
5.	Ethanol	15ml	15ml	15ml
6.	Glycerin	1-2 drop	1-2 drop	1-2 drop

Fig 2. Transdermal Patches (F1, F2, F3)

Evaluation of transdermal patches:

The prepared meloxicam transdermal patches were evaluated as mentioned below:

Physical appearance:

Every prepared patch was examined visually for color, clarity, smoothness, and flexibility.

Thickness of the patch:

The thickness of the patches was measured with a screw gauge at several locations.

Weight of the patch:

An electronic balance was used to determine the weight of each of the three patches that were removed from each batch. After that, the average weight of a single patch was calculated.

Folding endurance:

A tiny strip of patches measuring about 2 by 2 cm was folded repeatedly at the same spot until it broke in order to measure folding endurance. The value of folding endurance was determined by counting the number of times patches could be folded in the same spot without breaking(11).

Percentage flatness:

In order to measure the variation in length due to non-uniformity in flatness, longitudinal strips were cut from each film, one from the center and two from either side. The length of each strip was measured without the application of additional pressure, and the percentage constitution equivalent to 100% was calculated.

Percentage variation for strip=[measured length of strip/ length of center strip] ×100

Percentage moisture content:

Studies on moisture content showed that although a rise in the concentration of hydrophobic polymers caused the moisture content of the films to decrease, an increase in the concentration of hydrophilic polymers was exactly proportionate to the increase in the moisture content of the films. The produced formulations had a low moisture content, which may have contributed to their stability and decreased brittleness over time.

After being individually weighed, the produced films were stored for 24 hours at room temperature

in a desiccator filled with fused calcium chloride. After weighing the film once more, the following formula was used to determine its % moisture content:

Percentage moisture uptake = [final weight-initial weight / initial weight] x100

Moisture uptake:

The prepared patches were placed in desiccators with silica gel at room temperature for 24 hours. After that, they were weighed and moved to other desiccators where they were exposed to 75% RH using a saturated sodium chloride solution at 25°C. The provided formula was used to calculate the moisture uptake capacity.(11)

In vitro drug release studies:

The manufactured film was positioned on the cellulose membrane and connected to the diffusion cell. The diffusion cell is filled with the phosphate buffer solution. After 24hr the drug content of the sample was determined using a UV Spectrophotometer at 429nm.

Preparation Of Phosphate Buffer:

For preparation of buffer solution they the ingredient as shown in [Table 3] in volumetric flask.(12)

Table 3: Composition of Phosphate buffer pH 7.4

Sr. No.	Ingredient's	Quantity
1.	Disodium hydrogen phosphate	2.38g
2.	Potassium di-hydrogen phosphate	0.19g
3.	Sodium Chloride	8.0g
4.	Distilled Water	1000ml

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Description:

Meloxicam was physically examined for color and odor. It is yellow crystalline powder with mild, characteristic odor.

Solubility:

Meloxicam has very poor solubility in water. At room temperature about 25°C, the solubility is about 0.15–0.3 mg/ml.

In organic solvents like ethanol, methanol, and acetone, meloxicam has very good solubility; solubility varies according to the specific solvent used and temperature.

Melting point:

The melting point of meloxicam was found to be 258°C (496.4°F). This high melting point is consistent with its crystalline structure, which makes it stable under normal conditions but also contributes to its poor solubility in water. As melting point of drug was found nearby to standard value thus it is clear that the drug is pure.

Drug Interaction Studies:

UV-Visible interaction experiments were conducted to confirm the drug's interaction with the polymer. Both the drug with polymer and the

drug alone were observed in the UV-Visible overlay spectrum. It demonstrates that no drug-polymer interactions were discovered.

Evaluation Studies:

Physical appearance:

Sr. No.	Parameter	Observation
1	Color	Pale yellow
2	Clarity	Opaque
3	Smoothness	Smooth
4	Flexibility	Flexible

Thickness:

The thickness of the prepared patches varies between 0.257 mm ± 0.017 to 0.233 mm ± 0.013. Patch consistency is shown by low standard deviation values. [Table 4]

Weight Variation:

The weight of the prepared transdermal patches for different formulations ranged between 1.91mg ±

0.008 to 1.933mg ± 0.013 mg. The produced patches' weight uniformity variation fell within an acceptable limit. [Table 4]

Percentage flatness:

The flatness for F1 is: Mean=98.15% and Standard Deviation=±1.31%

The flatness for F2 is: Mean=100% and Standard Deviation=±0%

The flatness for F3 is: Mean=100.67% and Standard Deviation=±0.47%

Shown in [Table 4]

Folding endurance:

Folding endurance values varied between 49 ± 3.44 and 48 ± 3.63 . The outcome was deemed satisfactory, suggesting that the patches will remain intact and not shatter when put to use. [Table 4]

Table 4: Physic-Chemical Evaluation of Meloxicam Transdermal Patches.

Formulation Code	Thickness (mm)	Weight of Patch (mg)	Folding Endurance ± S. D	Flatness (%)
F1	0.257 mm ± 0.017	1.91 g ± 0.008	49 ± 3.44	7.133 ± 0.094
F2	0.233 mm ± 0.013	1.933 g ± 0.013	48 ± 3.63	6.0 ± 0
F3	0.233 mm ± 0.005	1.937 g ± 0.013	50 ± 4.54	7.833 ± 0.047

Percentage moisture content & Moisture uptake:

The results are depicted in Table 4: Moisture content and Moisture uptake of meloxicam transdermal patch

Compared to other preparations, patches made with HPC have higher percentages of moisture content and moisture uptake. This is due to HPC's great affinity for water and its hydrophilic character. As a result, patches made solely with HPC absorb more moisture, increasing their moisture content and uptake. On the other hand, patches made with less hydrophilic polymers or without HPC have reduced moisture content and moisture absorption. This is mostly because, in comparison to more hydrophobic or less water-attracting materials, HPC is more water-attracting and water-retaining.

In vitro drug release studies:

The drug's release from the polymeric transdermal film determines how much of the medication is available for blood absorption. The drug that makes it to the skin's surface is then subjected to standard permeation tests, which were carried out by affixing the transdermal patch to either the egg membrane or the artificial membrane that sits between the donor and receptor in vertical diffusion cells. The hydrophilic side of the membrane receives the transdermal system, while the lipophilic side comes into touch with the receptor fluid. The receiver chamber is constantly stirred and kept at a precise temperature, typically 32°C. The samples were taken out at identical intervals, and each time, the same volume of buffer was added. After diluting the samples, a UV

spectrophotometer was used to measure the absorbance. At each interval, the amount of drug penetrated per square centimeter is computed. The system's design, patch size, skin surface area, skin thickness, temperature, and other factors all affect drug release.

Fig 3. Franz Diffusion Cell

CONCLUSION:

Meloxicam transdermal patches were effectively formulated using HPC, showing promising outcomes in terms of drug release, moisture content, and moisture uptake. Because HPC is hydrophilic, patches made with it showed higher moisture retention, which flexibility. Meloxicam shows promising result, according to in vitro release experiments, which makes it a viable substitute for treating osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. This study suggests that HPC-based patches may improve bioavailability and reduce gastrointestinal adverse effects,

offering meloxicam a transdermal delivery method that works well.

REFERENCES

1. Rastogi V, Yadav P. Transdermal drug delivery system: An overview. *Asian J Pharm.* 2012;6(3):161.
2. Tiwary A, Sapra B, Jain S. Innovations in Transdermal Drug Delivery: Formulations and Techniques. *Recent Pat Drug Deliv Formul.* 2007 Feb 1;1(1):23–36.
3. Han T, Das DB. Potential of combined ultrasound and microneedles for enhanced transdermal drug permeation: A review. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* 2015 Jan;89:312–28.
4. Schoellhammer CM, Blankschtein D, Langer R. Skin permeabilization for transdermal drug delivery: recent advances and future prospects. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv.* 2014 Mar;11(3):393–407.
5. Donnelly RF, editor. *Microneedle-mediated transdermal and intradermal drug delivery.* Chichester, West Sussex: Wiley-Blackwell; 2012. 1 p.
6. Kretsos K, Kasting GB. A geometrical model of dermal capillary clearance. *Math Biosci.* 2007 Aug;208(2):430–53.
7. Donnelly RF, Singh TRR, Garland MJ, Migalska K, Majithiya R, McCrudden CM, et al. Hydrogel-Forming Microneedle Arrays for Enhanced Transdermal Drug Delivery. *Adv Funct Mater.* 2012 Dec 5;22(23):4879–90.
8. Arora A, Prausnitz MR, Mitragotri S. Micro-scale devices for transdermal drug delivery. *Int J Pharm.* 2008 Dec;364(2):227–36.
9. Tuan-Mahmood TM, McCrudden MTC, Torrisi BM, McAlister E, Garland MJ, Singh TRR, et al. Microneedles for intradermal and transdermal drug delivery. *Eur J Pharm Sci.* 2013 Dec;50(5):623–37.
10. Alkilani A, McCrudden MT, Donnelly R. *Transdermal Drug Delivery: Innovative Pharmaceutical Developments Based on Disruption of the Barrier Properties of the Stratum Corneum.* *Pharmaceutics.* 2015 Oct 22;7(4):438–70.
11. Trivedi D, Goyal A. Formulation and evaluation of transdermal patches containing dexketoprofen trometamol. *Int J Pharm Chem Anal.* 2020 Aug 28;7(2):87–97.
12. Dhamoon RK, Goyal RK, Popli H, Gupta M. Luliconazole-Loaded Thermosensitive Hydrogel as Aqueous based Nail Lacquer for the Treatment of Onychomycosis. *Drug Deliv Lett.* 2019 Oct 31;9(4):321–9.

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